

*The Impact of Tuning Africa Project on Post Graduate at
Mogadishu University
“Case Study of Educational Management Department”*

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Abstract

This paper explores the impact of tuning Africa project on post graduate program at Mogadishu University (case study: educational management department). The author also illustrates generic and subject-specific competences as of MU educational management department .

The study methodology includes a survey of some contemporary literatures related to the article, descriptive and correlation methods. The target population includes post graduate students of educational management department at Mogadishu University as purposive sample . For the data collection, the author used pre-self established questionnaire as well as SPSS for data analyzing.

Finally, the author demonstrates findings, conclusion and recommendation of the study in line with the research questions.

Keywords: Impact, Tuning Africa , Project, Post Graduate Programe, Mogadishu University Educational management.

1. 1 Introduction

When the civil war broke out and Somali state collapsed in 1991, there was a profound destruction of all vital institutions and facilities including universities, colleges, schools, and educational gap emerged which led to establishing private education to fill the gap and provide educational opportunities for different levels as Somali government during period was not able to function and provide even basic services.

Mogadishu university is considered as the foundation stone of private universities established in Somalia after collapse of the central government 1991. The idea of establishing Mogadishu University refers to 1993 when professors and lecturers of Somali National University, who had fled from homeland to the world, returned to the country and met with some prominent society figures to discuss and agree the idea of establishing a university in the country (despite of the difficult circumstances) in order to break a barriers of despair and disappointment to help Somali students who have completed secondary education and unable to continue their education because of civil war. For this regard, Mogadishu University was officially opened on 22 September 1997 in Mogadishu (MU, Introduction, 2017).

A huge number of students with different disciplines and different levels of bachelor and Master's degrees have graduated from MU, since its inception. The university has, thus, prepared new labor market entrants for the workforce and skills as these graduate students play an important role in building human capital for economic development of the country. MU Post graduate program aims at fostering cognitive

development, providing professional specialization, contributing to the development of research projects and solving problems of the society.

The program includes joint studies between MU and other universities, and MU special program for degrees of higher diploma, master and doctorate degrees. (MU, International Relations, 2017, p. 21)

The University seeks to improve the quality of education for its various stages. It is worth mentioning that the University participated in the program of Tuning Africa 2016 for curriculum reform based on competences at post graduate programme (Educational Management Department) as subject area group (SAG), which was successful.

From October 24th to 28th 2016 MU participated in the Ninth Conference on leadership and skills development for the African universities organized by the Association of African Universities in Accra, the capital city of Ghana. It is worth mentioning that prior to this conference in Accra, the Association had announced the success of eighteen Universities of Africa, including MU, in the completion of the study implemented by University of Deusto- Spain-Tuning Africa Project via the internet on the formulation of objectives and learning outcomes for postgraduate studies in the light of the educational competencies . The study took place from February to September 2016 (MU, International Relations, 2017, p. 13).

1.2 Problem Statement

Tuning Africa Project is an opportunity for African universities in general, and in Somalia in particular, .One of the main strategies of Mogadishu University is to raise the academic level according to the international standards and therefore offered a great attention to this

project, the of Educational Management Department participated in the project and there is a great desire to expand participation.

To know the impact of Tuning Africa Project on the department mentioned above is the most important of academic work and worthy to be studied. For this purpose, the author tries to answer this main question: “to what extent is the impact of Tuning Africa Project on Post Graduate programme of Educational Management Department at MU?

1.3 Significance of the Study

The importance of this article is that it is the first study conducted in Somalia according to the researcher's knowledge and could be an important reference for curriculum developers of higher education in Somalia.

1.4 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this article is to find out the level/impact of Turning Africa Project on Post Graduate Programme (Educational management Department) at Mogadishu University. The study targets teaching/learning approaches (student centered approach) and assessment modes as well as values taught.

1.5 Hypotheses

The researcher will test the following four hypotheses:

1. There is a significant relationship between teaching, learning approaches and learning outcomes (competences).
2. There is significant relationship teaching, learning approaches and learning values.
3. There is a significant relationship between assessment and learning outcomes (Competences).

4. There is a significant relationship between assessment and learning value.

2. literature Review

2.1 Concept of Tuning Africa

Definitions of Term Tuning

Three definitions encompass most of the reality of Tuning (University of Deusto, 2005, p. 3)

- Tuning is a project for the universities and by the universities.
- Tuning is a network of communities of learners.
- Tuning is a methodology for designing and implementing degree programmes.
- Tuning Africa Project There are two main projects in Africa (University of Deusto, 2005, p. 7)
- Feasibility Study on the Relevance of a Tuning Approach in higher education for Africa (1 March 2010 – 28 February 2011).
- Tuning Africa - EU Strategies Tuning Seminars (25 September 2011 – 31 March 2013).

There are 31 countries involved in Tuning Africa project: Algeria, Benin, Botswana, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Egypt, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Madagascar, Malawi, Mauritius, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, South Sudan, Tanzania, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe.

2.2 Definition of Generic Competences for Africa

The Tuning Africa Project began at the end of 2011 (Onana, et al., 2014) one of its first tasks was to define generic competences for Africa.

Each Subject Area Group (agricultural sciences, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, and medicine and teacher education) was asked to submit a list of the generic competences considered to be relevant to their perspective. As a starting point for preparing this list, they were given the thirty-one generic competences identified in Europe (Deusto, 2000) the twenty-seven generic competences identified in Latin America (<http://www.tuningal.org>), the thirty generic competences identified in Russia (<http://www.tuningrussia.org>) and a range of contributions from different participants in the project. At the first General Project Meeting, held in Yaoundé, Cameroon, in January 2012, the five Subject Area Groups (SAGs) working at that time discussed a proposal for the generic competences. The five groups presented a compilation of the generic competences in draft form, and the five coordinators agreed on a final list. List of generic competences agreed upon for Africa are as the following:

1. Ability for conceptual thinking, analysis and synthesis.
2. Professionalism, ethical values and commitment to Ubuntu (respect for the well-being and dignity of fellow human beings).
3. Capacity for critical evaluation and self-awareness.
4. Ability to translate knowledge into practice.
5. Objective decision-making and practical cost-effective problem solving.
6. Capacity to use innovative and appropriate technologies.
7. Ability to communicate effectively in both the official/national and the local languages.
8. Ability to learn how to learn and capacity for lifelong learning.

9. Flexibility, adaptability and ability to anticipate and respond to newsituations.
10. Ability for creative and innovative thinking.
11. Leadership, management and teamwork skills.
12. Communication and interpersonal skills.
13. Environmental and economic consciousness.
14. Ability to work in an intra- and intercultural and/or international context.
15. Ability to work independently.
16. Ability to evaluate, review and enhance quality.
17. Self-confidence, entrepreneurial spirit and skills.
18. Commitment to preserve African identity and cultural heritage

Analysis revealed the following top five generic competences for African higher education in all the identified disciplines (Hahn & Teferra, 2013, p. 16).

1. Ability for conceptual thinking, analysis and synthesis.
2. Professionalism, ethical values and commitment to UBUNTU.
3. Capacity for critical evaluation, and self-awareness.
4. Ability to translate knowledge into practice.
5. Objective decision making and practical cost effective problem solving.

2.3 Competency Based Curriculum

According to a report by U.S. Department of Education (2002), the importance of implementing competency-based initiatives in colleges and universities lies in two major reasons;

‘One main reason is that specific articulations of competencies inform and guide the basis of subsequent assessments at the course, program, and institutional levels. Secondly, specific competencies help faculty and students across campus, as well as other stakeholders such as employers and policymakers, to have a common understanding about the specific skills and knowledge those undergraduates should master as a result of their learning experiences’.

Therefore demand from the stakeholders is also leading to the emphasis on competency based education according to Jothika.(as cited in Choudaha, 2008).

Competency based curriculum summarizes academic and professional profiles, defines new objectives in the learning process, enhances learning environments and shifts the concept of learning as accumulation of knowledge to learning as a permanent attitude towards knowledge acquisition as described by Jothika.(as cited in Edwards et. Al, 2011).

The main idea of competency-based curriculum illustrates by Jothika.(as cited in Sudsomboon, 2007)

1. Instead of objectives, think “competencies”;
2. Instead of content, think outcomes;
3. Learner activities will be based on performance of learner and accomplishment of criteria;
4. Teaching activities are learner centered;
5. Formative evaluation is necessary).

The characteristics of competency-based education (CBE) are given by Globalization & Jothika.(as cited in Kouwenhoven, 2003).

– CBE is oriented to the professional practice.

- CBE is learner-centered and the learning process is central.
- CBE has a constructivist approach.
- In CBE the role of the teacher is that of a ‘cognitive guide’.
- CBE has learning environments focused on the development of competencies.
- CBE includes the development of generic competencies.
- In CBE assessment focused on competencies.
- In CBE curriculum development is based on the elaboration of profiles and identification of competencies.

2.4 Learning outcomes

The word “outcomes” will mean different things depending on the level of analysis and the kind of results of an academic experience that we are talking about (Tam, 2014, p. 4).

Learning outcomes are statements of what the teachers intends the learner know, do, understand and be able to demonstrate after the completion of learning. Detailed intended learning outcomes inform a single course unit or module (Serbati, 2015). Outcomes-based approach in higher education in recent decades there is a widespread interest in the outcomes of educational experiences and how those outcomes meet a variety of societal needs.

Learning outcomes are important for recognition...The principal question asked of the student or the graduate will therefore no longer be “what you do to obtain your degree?” but rather “what can you do now that you have obtained your degree?” This approach is of relevance to the labour market and is certainly more flexible when taking into account

issues of lifelong learning, non-traditional learning, and other forms of non-formal educational experiences (Tam, 2014, p. 2).

Literature on teaching in higher education has developed specific research fields about teacher conceptions of teaching and competence-based learning.

The concept of “competence” refers to a quality, ability, capacity or skill that is developed by and belongs to the student. Competences are developed in all course units and assessed at different stages of a programme. Some competences are subject-area related (specific to a field of studies), while others are generic, since students develop in their careers an integrated body of knowledge and skills from many different disciplines as well as transferable skills such as problem solving, critical and creative thinking, communication and leadership skills (Surian, 2014, p. 2).

In this context, the Tuning methodology offers concepts and operational tools to align Higher Education programmes with agreed learning outcomes and competences and qualification levels, answering to the need of labor market as well as the need of young people. To design courses based on intended learning outcomes (ILO) that are consistent and aligned with related teaching, learning and assessment techniques, it is crucial to apply a programme designing approach which optimizes the conditions for the quality of learning.

This approach requires a personal commitment by the teacher who focuses on the students’ learning outcomes and considers these the main goal of the learning and teaching process (Surian, 2014, p. 3).

The Main Characteristics of a Student-Centered Approach (Marinko, et al., 2016) The main characteristics of a student-centered approach are [MAO1] the considerations given to individual learners' experiences, perspectives, backgrounds, interests, capacities and needs Irena Marinko et al.(as cited in Schout & Harkema, 2008). Within this approach teachers mainly focus upon what students should learn and emphasize why (Irena Marinko et al. (as cited in Bransford & Bateman, 2002).

Teachers take into account the existing knowledge of students, as Irena Marinko et al. (as cited in Bransford, Brown, Cocking, 2000; Protheroe, 2007) provide different opportunities for students to learn, often change teaching methods, help students who have difficulties and consider their background. Teachers discuss with students which study activities lead to good results, expose students to looking for alternatives and try to find their own solutions.

Examination questions refer to real-life situation and do not lead to categorizing students with regard to their scores or grades. The basic conditions for an effective learning situation are the learning environment in which learners feel safe and accepted; numerous opportunities for students to confront new information, experiences, and personal discovery of new understandings that are all adapted to the individual students and their pace of learning Irena Marinko et al.(as cited in Mc Combs et al., 1997 .p.11).

**Table 1 Subject Specific Competences-Educational Management
Department at Mogadishu University**

Knowledge	Skills	Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to identify and analyses the constitutional characteristics of an organization. • Ability to choose how to respond to any situation, regardless of circumstances. • Capacity to identify, explore and use actual “web” ICT tools. • Ability to use critically how to organizing educational processes. • Ability to conduct scientific research methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership skills , • managing human recourses, • developing human recourses • critical thinking skills, • solve problem • planning skills, • setting and evaluating strategies, • finance management • Ability to conduct research in the field of education and apply the results in educational practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to foster social cooperation with various agencies and community members in order to promote the development of educational processes. • Ability to adopt the social value of the society. • Entrepreneurial spirit • Ethical commitment and professional attitude • Social responsibility and civic awareness

2.5 Intended Learning Outcomes at Mogadishu University

Based on generic competences of tuning of Africa, MU developed the following ILO’s for educational management department (MU, Syllabus of Educational Management Department , 2017) ability to:

- Provide concepts of management and their application in education environment.
- Apply statistics in education management.
- Recognize organizational behavior & Organization Theory in Education.

- Identify educational Technology
- To foster leadership skills
- To equip skills of planning, Solving problem, critical thinking and the assessment.
- To Apply scientific research in education
- To use practically howto organizing educational processes.
- To acquire experience of finance management and marketing in educational system
- To enhance the skills of human resource development.
- To improve communication skills in management.
- To choose title of thesis and prepare dissertation graduation
- To adopt the social value of the society.
- To foster ethical commitment and professional attitude
- Ability to foster social cooperation with various agencies and community members in order to promote the development of educational processes. Social responsibility and civic awareness the Concept of Competence.

According to (Nikolov, Shoikova, & Kovatcheva, 2014) the concept of competence can bridge the world of education, Training, knowledge management, and informal learning. There are a lot of examples of competence definitions.

The researchers in the field of competence have given various definitions for what competencies are: permanent distinctive traits and characteristics which determine performance; distinctive characteristics which differentiate the successful performer from the rest; an ability to reach goals; inner personality traits that allow a person to

cope better with a given task, role or situation; knowledge, skills, abilities and other characteristics demonstrated at work, etc.

Tuning Educational Structures in Europe defines competences as a dynamic combination of knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities.

The International Board of Standards for Training and Performance Instruction (IBSTPI) defines a competency as “a knowledge, skill, or attitude that enables one to effectively perform the activities of a given occupation or function to the standards expected in employment” (Nikolov, Shoikova, & Kovatcheva, 2014, p. 5).

As Nikolov, Shoikova, & Kovatcheva (ascited in Lisbon, 2010) write there are seven universal key competencies:

- Communication in the mother tongue;
- Communication in foreign languages;
- Competence in mathematics, science and technology;
- Digital competence;
- Ability to learn;
- Intercultural and social competencies, and civic competence;
- Intuitiveness and entrepreneurship.

Competency is an educated person who does not just “know” but can also “do” (Klein-Collins, 2013, p. 5). Competency refers to an element or combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes that an individual should be able to use to perform at work, school or other environments.

Teaching is one of the most complex professions that requires a combination of content knowledge, pedagogical skills and professional attitudes (UNESCO , 2016, p. 4).

2.6 Competency-Based Assessment

Competency-Based Assessment has become a predominant workplace reality, commonly used as an organizational development tool for the learner. Built upon earlier work on skills, abilities, and cognitive intelligence, it became a tool for understanding the talent and capability of human capital within an organization.

The benefit of collecting data of this kind is that the person gets to see a panorama of perceptions rather than just self-perception, thus affording a more complete picture (Jacquelyn & Baughman, 2012, p. 15).

Assessments are the only way that the students demonstrate knowledge and skills; thereby, having relevant and up to date assessments is essential to a CBE program (Cunningham, 2016, p. 12).

2.7 Challenges of Implementing Competency Based Curriculum

Regarding the implementation of the intended curriculum, it is extremely important that intended learning outcomes (competencies), teaching & learning approaches and assessment are aligned according to Jothika (as cited in Kouwenhoven, 2009). The higher education system as a whole should be flexible for ensuring proper alignment of competency based curriculum. Various regulatory authorities along with rules and regulations of universities may prohibit the experimentation and innovation in case of implementing competency based curriculum. Reforming a curriculum towards a more competence based approach implies more autonomy for the educational institution offering the educational programmers by Jothika.(as cited in Kouwenhoven, 2009).

3. Methodology

This research is descriptive study of correlational type. It investigates the relationship between Tuning Africa Project and post graduate Programme (Educational Management Department) at Mogadishu University. The Tuning Africa Project is an independent variable and post graduate Programme (Educational Management Department) is dependent variable.

The population sampled for this study focused on all graduates of educational management at MU (12) 2016/2017. Both combined pre-self established questionnaire was the instrument used in this study for the data collection. The author used SPSS for data analyzing .

4. Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) computer program was used in this study to analyze the data collected and formulated hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation statistics to determine the relationship that exists between Tuning Africa Project and post graduate program - Educational Management Department at Mogadishu University. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 as significance level.

Table 2: Teaching and Learning Approaches:

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		<i>Neutral</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Problem based learning	0	0	6	50	6			0	0	0
Small group based activities	0	0	6	50	2		4	33	0	0
Classdiscussions	0	0	7	58	2	17	3	25	0	0
Projects	0	0	9	75	0	0	3	25	0	0
Cooperating in research activities	0	0	9	75	0	0	3	25	0	0
Use of role plays	0	0	0	0	4	33	8	67	0	0
Textbooks	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	100	0	0
Additional slides	0	0	0	0	4	3	8	7	0	0
Researcharticles	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	12	100
Popular scientificliterature	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	100	0	0

The table above describes the respondents towards teaching and learning approaches. The 50% of the respondents agreed strongly that the lecturers conducted, problem based learning and small group based activities methods, 58% of the participants agreed that class discussions are conducted meanwhile 75% of them agreed that project and cooperating research methods are used and the text books are followed 100% while slides are not employed, 67% of the participants disagreed. Finally, the majority of the respondents 100% disagreed that research articles and popular scientific literature are used in teaching and learning process.

Table 3: Assessment

Statement	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Summative	12	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Formative	12	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Flexible	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	100
Making feedback directed to wards the task	0	0	6	50	6	50	0	0	0	0
Discussion on strengths and weaknesses	0	0	0	0	11	92	1	8	1	
Explaining mistakes advice how to improve	0	0	6	50	6	50	0	0	0	0
Help to focus on skills relating to a deep approach to learning	0	0	6		6	50	0	0	0	0

Table 3 shows that the common use of assessing ILO's in intended learning outcomes are summative and formative 100%. There is no any flexibility of assessment while the making feedback directed to the task is 50% and the discussion on strengths ad weakness rated 50% as well as the level of explaining mistakes and helping to focus on skills to deep approach to learning proportionally are 50%.

Table 4: Learning Outcomes (Competences)

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		<i>Neutral</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Capacity to identify, analyses the characteristics of educational organization	0	0	4	33	8	67	0	0	0	0
Ability to choose how respond any situation _of circum stances	0	0	5	42	7	58	0	0	0	0
Capacity to identify and use actual web ICT tools	2	17	3	25	6	50	1	8	0	0
Ability to identify use critically educational processes	2	17	3	25	6	50	1	8	0	0
Leadership skills	2	17	3	25	6	50	1	8	0	0
Managing human resources	0	0	4	33	7	58	1	8	0	0
Critical thinking skills	0	0	4	33	7	58	1	8	0	0
Solve problem	3	25	5	42	4	33	0	0	0	0
Planningskills	5	42	4	33	3	25	0	0	0	0
Setting and evaluating strategies	2		3	25	6	50	1	8	0	0
Ability toconductresearch in educationalpractice	2	17	3	25	6	50	1	8	0	0
Ability to foster social cooperation in order to promote educational processes	1	8	3	25	7	58	1	8	0	0

Table 4. Indicates the level of learning outcomes hat student acquired during teaching and learning process. The most ratio concentrated on agree and neutral alternatives 17% to 58% from responses of the

population study, this shows positive results of learning outcomes level such as capacity of analyzing critically characteristics of educational organization, using actual web ICT tools, managing human resources, critical thinking skills, Solving problems, conducting researches and evaluating strategies in educational practice as well as leadership skills and ability to foster social cooperation in order to promote educational processes.

Table 5: Values

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>		<i>Agree</i>		<i>Neutral</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Ability to adopt the value of the society	12	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ethical commitment and professional attitude	5	42	7	58	0	0	0	0	0	0
Social responsibility and civic awareness	8	67	4	33	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5 illustrates the level of value skills of the students where 100% of respondents agreed strongly that they have ability to adopt the value of the society and 58% agreed that they have ethical commitment and professional attitude and 67% of respondents agreed strongly that they have social responsibility and civic awareness. This highlights positive results of values acquisition.

5. Testing Hypotheses

The researcher tested hypotheses study with 0.05 as significance level. The results of the study are presented as below:

Ha₁. There a significant relationship between teaching, learning approaches and learning outcomes (competences).

Table 6. Correlational Analysis of Teaching, Learning and Learning Outcomes (Competences)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Calculated Value</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision</i>
IV1. Teaching and Learning Approaches	.538	.036	Ha 1. accepted
DV 1. Learning Outcomes			

Table 6 shows that calculated value of correlation of 0.538 is positive value of correlation and the sig value of 0.036 is less than at 0.05 level of significance, thus, the hypothesis which states there is significance relationship between teaching, learning approaches and learning outcomes (competences) was accepted.

Ha₂. There is a significant relationship teaching, learning approaches and learning values.

Table 7. Correlational Analysis of Teaching, Learning and Learning Values.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Calculated Value</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision</i>
IV1. Teaching and Learning Approaches	.605*	.018	Ha 2. accepted
DV 2. Learning values			

Table 7 describes that the level of correlation between teaching, learning and learning values is 0.605 and the sig value of 0.018 is less than at 0.05 level of significance, thus, the hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between teaching, learning approaches and learning values was accepted.

Ha₃. There is a significant relationship between assessment and learning outcomes (Competences).

Table 8. Correlational Analysis of assessment and learning outcomes (Competences)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Calculated Value</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision</i>
IV2. Assessment	.583	.030	Ha 3. accepted
DV 1. Learning Outcomes			

Table 8 shows that calculated correlation of 0.583 is positive correlation and the sig value of 0.030 is less than at 0.05 level of significance. This means that the hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between assessment and learning outcomes was accepted.

Ha₄. There is a significant relationship between assessment and learning values.

Table 9. Correlational Analysis of assessment and Learning Values

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Calculated Value</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Decision</i>
IV2. Teaching and Learning Approaches	-.356	.141	H 4. rejected
DV 2. Learning Values			

Table 9 shows that calculated value of correlation of -0.356 is negative value of correlation and the sig value 0.141 is greater than at 0.05 level of significance, thus, the hypothesis which states there is a significant relationship between assessment and learning values was rejected.

6. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data collected that there is relationship between Tuning Africa Project and Post graduate at Mogadishu University, particularly educational management department. The study found out the relationship between teaching, learning approaches and learning outcomes (competences) and values. The study has also revealed the relationship between assessment and learning outcomes (competences) while there is no relationship between assessment and value.

7. Recommendations

According to the findings of the study, the following recommendations are presented:

- Continuity of training on good practice competences-based student-centered approach in higher education in accordance with Tuning Africa to enhance skills of lecturers.
- Strengthening the sources and required materials by teaching methods in higher education.
- Flexibility and developing assessment modes based on competences based student centered.
- Expand Tuning Africa Approach to other specializations/faculties at Mogadishu University.

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